
Professional Development Programmes as Predictors of Teachers' Job Performance in Public Secondary Schools in Anambra State

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Abstract

The study examined professional development programmes as predictors of teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Two research questions guided the study and two null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. The study was a correlational research design. The population of the study was 267 principals in the public secondary schools from the six Education Zones in Anambra State. The entire population of 267 principals was used for the study. Census sampling was used for the study because the population was small and manageable by the researcher. Two researcher-structured instruments were used for data collection: Professional Development Programmes Questionnaire (PDPQ) and Teachers' Job Performance Questionnaire (TJPQ). The instruments were subjected to face and construct validation. Face validation was done by three experts, while construct validation was carried out by Principal Component Analysis (PCA) approach. The reliability of the instrument was done using Cronbach Alpha technique and the average coefficient values 0.82 for PDPQ and 0.85 for TJPQ were obtained and considered highly reliable and suitable for the study. Simple linear regression statistical tool was used to answer the research questions and test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The findings of the study revealed that teachers' orientation and mentorship positively and significantly predicted teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State. The study concluded that professional development programmes positively and significantly predicts teachers' job performance in secondary schools in Anambra State. Based on the findings, the study recommended among others that policy makers should develop and implement clear policies that prioritize continuous professional development and performance appraisal as key strategies for enhancing teachers' job performance with adequate back up of adequate funding and incentives provided for teachers' training programmes in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Keywords: Professional Development Programmes, Teachers' Job Performance, Public Secondary School

Introduction

In the school system, teachers' job performance could be described as the duties performed by teachers at any given time in school geared towards achieving both the daily school and classroom objectives and the entire set goals and objectives of education. Such duties include among others: covering of scheme of work adequately, attending community events, giving and marking of continuous assessment regularly, hosting parent-teacher meeting, teachers with advanced training mentor other teachers, preparing plan of any lesson to be taught to mention but a few. Adinna and Onyekwelu (2021) added that teachers performs other activities including managing stubborn students in the class without distorting teaching and learning and serving as coach to students.

Teachers' job performance referred to an act of accomplishing or executing a given task. Osuji et al. (2022) defined teachers' job performance as duties performed by teachers at a particular period in the school system in order to achieve school stated goals. As noted by Ifediorah Okeke (2023), Okoli et al. (2024), teachers' job performance could be measured through teachers' job satisfaction and job attitudes such as job commitment, feelings of job challenge, job meaningfulness and job responsibility. Okaforcha and Ifediorah Okeke (2020) asserted that, when an individual is satisfied, their job performance might increase and tend to be more committed to their work. In the educational setting, Ifediorah Okeke (2022), Manafa & Adinna (2023) noted that job performance comprises what a teacher does in the school for achievement of school goals and the outcomes of his or her actions which are measurable through work. Adinna et al. (2024) asserted that teachers' job performance is understood as teachers' effectiveness in fulfilling their roles and responsibilities to enhance educational outcomes.

Teachers' job performance acts as an avenue for monitoring and evaluation. Chukwueze (2023) noted teachers' job performance as changes in teachers' practice, example, knowledge, understanding, skills, behaviour, attitudes, values and convictions. Ughamadu et al. (2024) asserted that teachers' job performance seems to be below expectation and has invariably been affecting the set objectives of education. As noted by Okafor & Adinna (2023), and Azubuike (2024), there is need for an improvement in teachers' development so as to get them committed to their work to yield quality output. Otherwise, the decline in their development may lead to teachers' negative attitude to their work such as lateness to school, lack of meaningful contribution towards school work, poor class management, non- preparation of lesson note, truancy and opting out of the profession at a slightest opportunity without regret.

Contextually, teachers' job performance means the accomplishment of roles outlined for teachers in the school. It is how a teacher behaves while teaching and is related to their effectiveness. This involves the teaching-learning process that takes place in the classroom which include; provision and presentation of suitable lesson, use of appropriate methods of teaching, and use of current and proper instructional aides as well as assessment of students' performance. Teachers' job performance can be improved through professional development programmes.

The aim of professional development programmes is to keep the staff up-to-date on the latest development in the field, or ensure the promotion of professional growth, help to improve pedagogical skills, keep teachers abreast with new knowledge, meet particular needs, such as curriculum development and orientation, help in leadership responsibility, help to improve mutual respect among teachers and recognize the need of modern teaching

methods. Osuji et al. (2022) defined professional development as the development of individuals in their professional roles through formal or informal experiences such as seminars, workshops, conferences, reading professional publications etc. Ohamaobi et al. (2024) submitted that professional development programmes are therefore, organized to keep teachers current, vibrant and versatile, particularly in this age of socio-economic, political, scientific and technological changes, thereby, enhancing the job committed and performance of teachers.

Professional development has been accepted as an effective method of increasing the knowledge of skills of teachers in order to enable teachers to teach more effectively. Staff development programmes refer to all the activities intended to improve and increase the skills and capabilities as well as the performance of school personnel (teachers). Anachuna and Obi (2022) noted that regardless of all employee pre-service training and level of education there is the need for every staff and employee in an organization to constantly and regularly renew, upgrade, expand and update his/her skill, knowledge and ability as well as capability. Onyekwelu (2024) noted that staff development programmes are necessary for teachers as quality assurance strategies to ensure that teachers become highly competent in their job execution. This is because any teacher that is not growing in skill and knowledge cannot keep pace with their relationship with the teaching profession. Onyekwelu (2024) further mentioned that staff development can be in form of orientation, conferences, seminar, in-service training and mentorship among others.

Staff professional development consists of all managerial strategies and staff trainings targeted at improving and updating the skills and knowledge of teachers which prepare them for future and new positions. Nwagbata (2024) noted that professional development programme helps teachers to cope with increasing new trends and innovation in the education system. Staff professional development practices include workshops, refresher courses, in-service training, orientation, seminars, distance learning programmes, personal enrichment courses, conferences, coaching, symposia and mentoring. Ohamobi et al. (2024) insisted that organizing professional development for teachers helps to equip them with emerging trend and strategies in the teaching profession. Onyekwelu (2024) posited that inadequate provision of professional development in educational institutions could reduce their enthusiasm in the teaching profession and this could affect their morale, attitude to work, commitment and satisfaction. Obi et al. (2024) observed that professional development programmes is the provision of skills to enable staff members effectively performs their jobs. Obi et al. (2024) further noted that the types of professional development programmes include: simple orientation programme, organized visit, seminars and conferences, participatory management, internal training programmes, formal professional library education and short courses and all these training programmes can help both professional and para-professional staff to be current with new knowledge and development in the field.

Contextually, the researcher defined professional development programme as a structured programme of career training and continuing education that helps teachers develop new skills, stay current and advance their careers in teaching. It is a process, programmes and activities through which every school develops, enhances and improves the skills, competencies and overall performance of its teachers. Generally speaking, development programmes through in-service, conference, workshop, seminars and mentoring offer one of the most promising ways of improving classroom instruction. In this study, professional development programmes was delimited to orientation and mentorship.

Orientation of teachers is the process of bringing teachers up-to-date on recent trends, school policies, job roles and responsibilities and other school attributes and concepts that will help them transit efficiently into the position. Nwagbata (2024) opined that work orientation is a process for giving employees important information about their workspace, equipment, pay, benefits and dress code. In the words of Ejiofor (2022), orientation is a special kind of training designed to help new teachers to learn about their tasks, to be introduced to their co-workers and to settle in their work situation. Traditionally, orientation means describing to individuals the latest changes in the organization's history, structure, fringe benefits, rules and regulations. Agubosim and Nwuba (2022) opined that job orientation is a process for giving new employees important information about their workspace, equipment, pay, benefits, and dress code. Agubosim and Nwuba further noted that a more progressive approach is to view orientation as an opportunity to communicate the school's vision and values, shape the workers' values and integrate them into the school's structure. Orientation is a special kind of training designed to help new teachers to learn about their tasks, to be introduced to their co-workers and to settle in their work situation (Onuorah & Onyekwelu, 2024). Traditionally, orientation means describing to the new employee the organization's history, structure, fringe benefits, rules and regulations. Chukwueze (2023) averred that a more progressive approach is to view orientation as an opportunity to communicate the school's vision and values, shape the new teachers' values and integrate him/her into the school's structure. It can take the form of mentorship.

Mentoring is having a more experienced teachers provide help and support to less experienced teachers to improve their job performance. Buba et al. (2022) submitted that mentoring promotes individuals' awareness and refinement of their own professional development by providing and recommending structured opportunities for reflection and observation. Anachuna and Emegwa (2024) inferred that mentoring is a confidential process through which an experienced professional provides another with information, support, feedback and assistance for the purpose of refining present skills, developing new ones and enhancing problem solving and decision making in a way that promotes professional development. In the words of Ohamaobi et al. (2024), mentorship is the experience of a skilled and competent teacher through a working relationship between less experienced staff. The use of mentorship is explored to put new staff on the right course of the conduct and ways to carry out responsibilities given to them (Aminu et al., 2023). All the professional development programmes and activities are aimed at improving teachers' job performance in school.

The quality of teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State has been put in doubts due to the poor attitudes manifested by some secondary school teachers who appear to be non-committed to their jobs. Some public school teachers do not go to school on time, some rarely teach students, writing notes of lesson appears to be a boring task to some teachers who ought to have been professionally behaved. Onyekwelu and Adinna (2022) notice that, some teachers are poorly discharging their teaching duties while their principals are less concerned as regards to the level of job performance of their teachers. Oguejiofor (2023) alongside Edo and Johnson (2024) have observed the truant nature of some secondary school teachers as exhibited in their poor attitude towards instructional duties, lateness to work, inconsistency attendance to school or classes, poor record keeping attitude and their poor disciplinary attitudes. Thus, there is need to examine professional development programmes as predictors of teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of the study was to examine professional development programmes as predictors of teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. Determine the predictive value of orientation on teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State.
2. Find out the predictive value of mentoring on teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the predicative value of orientation on teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State?
2. What is the predicative value of mentoring on teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. Orientation does not significantly predict teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State.
2. Mentoring does not significantly predict teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Research Methods

The study was carried out in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Two research questions guided the study and two null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. The study was a correlational research design. The population of the study was 267 principals in the 267 public secondary schools from the six Education Zones in Anambra State. The entire population of 267 principals was used for the study. Census sampling was used for the study because the population was small and manageable by the researcher. Two researcher-structured instruments were used for data collection: Professional Development Programmes Questionnaire (PDPQ) and Teachers' Job Performance Questionnaire (TJPQ). The instruments were subjected to face and construct validation. Face validation was done by three experts, while construct validation was carried out by Principal Component Analysis (PCA) approach. The reliability of the instrument was done using Cronbach Alpha technique and the average coefficient values 0.82 for PDPQ and 0.85 for TJPQ were obtained and considered highly reliable and suitable for the study. Direct method of data administration was utilized by the researcher together with six research assistants. Out of 267 copies of the instrument administered, 265(99%) of the instrument were correctly completed and returned. Simple linear regression statistical tool was used to answer the research questions and test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

Result

Research Question One: What is the predictive value of orientation on teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State?

Table 1: Summary of Simple Regression Analysis on the Predictive Value of Orientation on Teachers' Job Performance in Public Secondary Schools in Anambra State

	Unstandardized	Std. Dev.	Standardized
	β	β	β
Constant	30.817	3.112	
Orientation	0.673	0.328	0.652
R	0.652		
R ²	0.595		
Adj. R ²	0.531		

The summary of the simple regression analysis as shown in Table 1 indicated that the regression line has a positive intercept as presented by the constant value of 30.817. This means that if all the variables are held constant or fixed (zero) at the expense of orientation, teachers' job performance will be valued at 31%. The analysis showed that orientation positively predict teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State as shown by the regression coefficient ($R = 0.652$). Furthermore, the standardized beta is also values at $\beta = 0.652$ which revealed that orientation is a positive predictor of teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State. This implies that a unit increase in orientation led to 0.652(65%) increase in teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State. The coefficient of determination (R^2) value of 0.595 indicated that the explanatory power of the variable was moderately strong. This implies that 60% of the variations in teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State were accounted for by the variations in orientation. The adjusted R^2 supported the claim of the R^2 with a value of 0.531 indicating that 53% of the total variation in teachers' job performance was explained by orientation. Thus, adjusted R^2 supports the statement that the explanatory power of teachers' job performance moderately depends on orientation in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Research Question Two: What is the predictive value of mentoring on teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State?

Table 2: Summary of Simple Regression Analysis on the Predictive Value of Mentoring on Teachers' Job Performance in Public Secondary Schools in Anambra State

	Unstandardized	Std. Dev.	Standardized
	β	β	B
Constant	29.348	3.124	
Mentoring	0.725	0.239	0.707
R	0.707		
R ²	0.624		
Adj. R ²	0.578		

The summary of the simple regression analysis as shown in Table 2 indicated that the regression line has a positive intercept as presented by the constant value of 29.348. This means that if all the variables are held constant or fixed (zero) at the expense of mentoring, teachers' job performance will be valued at 29%. The analysis showed that orientation positively predict teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State as shown by the regression coefficient ($R = 0.707$). In addition, the standardized beta is also values at $\beta = 0.707$ which revealed that mentoring is a positive predictor of teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State. This implies that a unit improvement in mentoring led to 0.707(71%) improvement in teachers' job performance in

public secondary schools in Anambra State. The coefficient of determination (R^2) value of 0.624 indicated that the explanatory power of the variable was high. This implies that 62% of the variations in teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State were accounted for by the variations in mentoring. The adjusted R^2 supported the claim of the R^2 with a value of 0.578 indicating that 58% of the total variation in teachers' job performance was explained by mentoring. Thus, adjusted R^2 supports the statement that the explanatory power of teachers' job performance moderately depends on mentoring in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis One

H₀₁: Orientation does not significantly predict teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Table 3: Test of Significance on the Simple Regression Analysis on Significant Predication of Orientation on Teachers' Job Performance in Public Secondary Schools in Anambra State.

	Unstandardized β	Std. Dev. β	Standardized β	t-value	p-value
Constant	30.817	3.112		24.105	0.000
Orientation	0.673	0.328	0.652	21.873	0.000
R	0.652				
R^2	0.595				
Adj. R^2	0.531				
F	31.705				0.000

The summary of the test of significance of simple regression analysis as shown in Table 3 showed that the simple regression coefficient (R) is 0.652 while the R^2 is 0.595 and Adjust R^2 is 0.531. The F-ratio associated with regression is 31.705, the t-test is 21.873 and the p-value = 0.000. Since p-value (0.000) is less than the specified level of significance 0.05, the study therefore rejected the null hypothesis that orientation does not significantly predict teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State and accepted the alternative hypothesis that orientation significantly predicts teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Hypothesis Two

H₀₂: Mentoring does not significantly predict teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Table 4: Test of Significance on the Simple Regression Analysis on Significant Predication of Mentoring on Teachers' Job Performance in Public Secondary Schools in Anambra State

	Unstandardized β	Std. Dev. β	Standardized β	t-value	p-value
Constant	29.348	3.124		31.532	0.000
Mentoring	0.725	0.239	0.707	25.486	0.000
R	0.707				
R^2	0.624				
Adj. R^2	0.578				
F	42.351				0.000

The summary of the test of significance of simple regression analysis as shown in Table 4 showed that the simple regression coefficient (R) is 0.707 while the R^2 is 0.624 and Adjust R^2 is 0.578. The F-ratio associated with regression is 42.351, the t-test is 25.486 and the p-value = 0.000. Since p-value (0.000) is less than the specified level of significance 0.05, the study therefore rejected the null hypothesis that mentoring does not significantly predict teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State and accepted the alternative hypothesis that mentoring significantly predicts teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Discussion of the Findings

Findings on the predictive value of orientation on teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State revealed that orientation has a positive predictive value of 0.652(65%) on teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State. This means that increase in orientation will bring about 65% increases in teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State. The study also showed that orientation significantly predicted teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State. The finding is in agreement with the findings of Ejiofor (2022) that attending orientation and conferences had significantly influenced teachers' effectiveness in secondary schools. The finding of the study is in agreement with the views of Agubosim and Nwuba (2022) findings that orientation and in-service training have improved the performance of teachers in secondary schools. Chukwueze (2023) found out that seminars and orientation correlated significantly with teachers' effectiveness and therefore concluded that most of the teachers who had various opportunities to attend well organized seminars, conferences and orientation really enhanced their productivity. Nwagbata (2024) findings showed that teachers' seminar, in-service training and orientation training have a positive and significant relationship between with teachers' job performance in public senior secondary schools in Anambra State. In agreement, Onyekwelu (2024) findings revealed a very high positive relationship between staff development strategy and teachers' job effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State. This suggested that when principals of public secondary schools prioritize and invest in the professional development of teachers, it significantly enhances their effectiveness in fulfilling their roles.

Findings on the predictive value of mentoring on teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State revealed that mentoring has a positive predictive value of 0.707(71%) on teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State. This means that increase in mentorship will bring about 72% increases in teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State. The study also showed that teachers' mentoring significantly predicted teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State. The finding is in agreement with the findings of Buba et al. (2022) that mentoring gives teachers' opportunities to advance in their career which thus makes them more likely to stay in the job and reduces their truant nature. The findings aligned with Anachuna and Obi (2022) findings that principals maintain a learning relationship with their teachers with the view of improving teachers' effective teaching in schools. This finding is in line with Ngabirano et al. (2023) who submitted that principals provide teachers with instructions on specific details and examples of teaching techniques that constitute excellent practice and also provided demonstration lessons. The findings of Aminu et al. (2023) evidenced that mentoring activities for teachers when properly practiced by school leaders improves teachers' performance. Ohamaobi et al. (2024) indicated that there is a positive and significant relationship between mentoring and teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State. This means that professional development helps to get teachers'

committed to their work for the actualization of school set goals. Onyekwelu (2024) agreed that a new teacher in a school system can be confused if not guided and this can lead to frustration and not having a positive outcome which will amount to withdrawal in activity. In addition, Anachuna and Emegwa (2024) advocated that new teachers find themselves confused and out of place when they get to a new environment hence the importance of mentoring which is aimed at retraining talented and creative teachers to ensure the desired productivity is attained. Therefore, the essence of mentoring is to assist a new teacher develops specific abilities that will enhance their professional and personal growth which will aid them become productive in the school system.

Conclusion

The study concluded that professional development programmes are positive and significant variables that enhance teachers' job performance in secondary schools in Anambra State.

Recommendations

Based on the empirical findings of the study, the following recommendations are made:

1. Policy makers should develop and implement clear policies that prioritize continuous professional development and performance appraisal as key strategies for enhancing teachers' job performance with adequate back up of adequate funding and incentives provided for teachers' training programmes in public secondary schools in Anambra State.
2. Principals should constantly plan for teachers' development through mentorship so as to inculcate in them the best teaching methodology needed in the teaching profession for continual improvement of teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

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